

Advancing responsible research assessment at the University of Bristol: a holistic, context-sensitive CoARA action plan (2026–2031)

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1. Introduction

- 1.1 The University of Bristol is committed to transforming the way we assess research. Our commitment is grounded in the [CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#), the [Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#) and the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#), all of which we have signed. These frameworks share a common purpose: to ensure that research assessment focuses on the quality, integrity and openness of research, and on the conditions that enable researchers and research-enablers to thrive. This work aligns with the University's wider commitments under national and international research concordats and agreements, supporting high standards in research integrity, open research, equity, inclusion, researcher development and the creation of supportive and enabling research environments. This plan sets out how the University will further embed these principles in practice through a phased, evidence-led and participatory programme of reform.
- 1.2 This work also aligns with the University's commitment to equitable and responsible international research partnerships, including engagement with the principles set out in the [Africa Charter for Transformative Research Collaborations](#), an Africa-centred framework for more equitable global research partnerships co-created with African higher education bodies and facilitated by the [Perivoli Africa Research Centre \(PARC\)](#). Through this, the University recognises the importance of fair recognition of contributions, inclusive collaboration practices, and equitable partnership models, which are closely aligned with the aims of responsible research assessment.
- 1.3 Globally, there is growing recognition that traditional approaches to research assessment can create unintended consequences that undermine research quality, the wellbeing of researchers and research enablers, and the effectiveness of the research system as a whole. These approaches have often relied heavily on narrow indicators, such as publication venue, citation counts, or grant income, which may not fully reflect the quality, integrity or the full range of contributions that enable research to take place. As a result, these approaches can:
- Incentivise quantity over quality, rigour or originality.
 - Disadvantage certain disciplines, career stages, roles or research approaches.
 - Overlook important contributions such as collaboration, interdisciplinary work, mentorship, open research, policy engagement, and the intellectual, technical and professional contributions of those who enable research.

Example 1: Supporting early career researchers

[Before responsible assessment](#)

An early career researcher feels pressure to prioritise publishing in specific journals associated with high impact factors, even when other venues would better reach their intended audience.

[With responsible assessment](#)

Assessment focuses on the quality, originality and contribution of their work, alongside broader contributions such as collaboration, open research and engagement. The researcher can make publication decisions based on scholarly value rather than perceived metric advantage.

- Create pressure to prioritise metrics or reputation indicators over meaningful scholarly and research-enabling contributions.
- Reduce transparency, fairness and trust in assessment processes.

1.4 These challenges have led to a coordinated global movement to reform research assessment, recognising that more meaningful, context-sensitive approaches are essential to strengthening research quality, rigour and integrity. This action plan forms part of that effort, setting out how the University of Bristol will contribute to and benefit from reform in ways that reflect our institutional context, priorities and values.

1.5 This five-year plan is structured around three phases that will guide the University's transition toward more responsible and coherent research assessment. Phase 1 centres on understanding our current practices and creating the foundations for reform. Phase 2 focuses on designing, piloting and embedding a more holistic and context-sensitive approach to research assessment across the University, including aligning key processes such as promotion, annual review, strategic planning and activity related to the [Research Excellence Framework \(REF\)](#) within a coherent framework. Phase 3 is a period of evaluation and future planning, ensuring that progress is reviewed and that the University of Bristol remains aligned with the CoARA commitments.

1.6 Together, these phases support our overarching aims of recognising the full breadth of research contributions, strengthening qualitative judgement, ensuring responsible and transparent use of data, and embedding consistent, fair and inclusive assessment practices across the institution. This approach will also strengthen transparency and trust by clarifying how evidence is interpreted and applied in practice, supporting consistent implementation of existing principles, and ensuring that disciplinary and institutional contexts are appropriately considered.

1.7 By advancing responsible research assessment, the University aims to:

- Strengthen the quality and integrity of research evaluation.
- Support fairer and more inclusive recognition of diverse contributions.
- Improve transparency and consistency in decision-making.
- Reduce unintended pressures associated with narrow assessment practices.
- Support researchers and research-enablers to focus on meaningful, high-quality work.
- Align institutional practice with international best practice.

Example 2: Recognising research-enabling contributions

Before responsible assessment

A research software engineer develops and maintains widely used research infrastructure that supports multiple projects and teams. However, because their contribution does not take the form of traditional research outputs or grant income, it is not consistently recognised in processes such as performance review or institutional planning. This can undervalue work that is essential to research quality and capability.

With responsible assessment

Assessment frameworks recognise the full range of contributions that enable research to take place, including technical development, infrastructure and collaborative expertise. These contributions are appropriately considered alongside other forms of evidence in recruitment, promotion and review, supporting fairer recognition and strengthening the University's research capability.

- 1.8 Success will be reflected in clearer, fairer and more consistent assessment practices, increased confidence among those involved in assessment, and improved alignment between institutional processes and responsible research assessment principles.
- 1.9 We will draw on the [INORMS SCOPE Framework](#) to guide the design of our reforms so that evaluation remains situated, co-designed and proportionate to purpose. SCOPE is a recognised, structured approach that supports responsible research assessment and is highlighted within the CoARA reform journey as a practical method for developing criteria, tools and processes that fit local contexts and avoid unintended consequences.
- 1.10 CoARA advises institutions to avoid the inappropriate use of rankings and ranking-derived indicators as proxies for research quality in assessment. At the same time, the University recognises that reputation, benchmarking and international visibility are important for institutional strategy and external positioning. We will therefore develop a clear and transparent framework to support the appropriate and contextual use of rankings, indicators and other evaluative information, while aligning internal research assessment with responsible research assessment principles. This work will help clarify how such information should be used proportionately and responsibly to reduce inappropriate trickle-down effects.
- 1.11 The University of Bristol is also an active contributor to national and international work on responsible research assessment. The University is one of the co-leads of the [UK CoARA National Chapter](#), which provides a space for institutions to share practice, coordinate approaches and support collective progress across the sector. This leadership role strengthens our own approach and ensures that Bristol both contributes to, and learns from, the wider international community working to improve research assessment.
- 1.12 The University affirms that responsible research assessment must operate in full respect of academic freedom of expression and freedom of speech. These principles are essential to the advancement of knowledge and to the integrity of the research process. Reforming research assessment is not intended to constrain intellectual inquiry, academic debate or disciplinary diversity. Rather, it seeks to ensure that assessment practices support independent thinking, recognise diverse contributions, and enable researchers and research-enablers to pursue rigorous, creative and meaningful work without inappropriate pressure or constraint.

Example 3: Supporting fair and responsible REF output selection

Before responsible assessment

REF output review processes rely heavily on proxy indicators such as journal rankings, citation counts or perceived prestige and may involve narrow internal selection processes. Researchers may feel pressure to prioritise outputs perceived as REF-eligible rather than pursuing innovative or longer-term research.

With responsible assessment

REF output review processes are supported by clearer principles, appropriate use of indicators and informed qualitative judgement. Outputs are assessed on their intrinsic quality, originality and contribution, with appropriate disciplinary expertise and contextual understanding. This helps ensure fairer selection processes, reduces inappropriate reliance on proxies, and supports a healthier and more sustainable research culture.

2. Scope and governance

- 2.1 **Scope:** In line with the CoARA Agreement, and for the purposes of this action plan, research assessment includes the evaluation of researchers, projects and units for any purposes, including but not limited to recruitment, promotion, professional development review, performance management, internal funding and awards, research planning, institutional recognition and communications activities and the selection of outputs and other submission content for the REF.
- 2.2 **Governance:** Chaired by the Director of Research Excellence, the Responsible Research Assessment Working Group (RRA WG) provides institutional leadership for, and leads delivery of, this plan. It reports to the Research Culture Committee (RCC) and, through it, to the University Research Committee (URC) and the Pro Vice-Chancellor for Research and Innovation (PVC RI). Core membership draws from Global Engagement, Human Resources, Library Services, Perivoli Africa Research Centre (PARC), Research and Innovation Services, Strategic Communications and Marketing, and Strategy, Planning and Transformation. This governance structure ensures both institutional oversight and close integration with wider research culture and strategy processes.

Example 4: Supporting fair and informed recruitment and promotion decisions

Before responsible assessment

Institutional guidance emphasises assessing research on its quality and contribution. However, in practice, hiring or promotion panels may rely heavily on journal prestige, institutional reputation or other proxy indicators, particularly where there is uncertainty, time pressure or limited confidence in applying qualitative judgement. This can lead to inconsistent implementation of existing principles.

With responsible assessment

Panels are supported through clearer frameworks, practical guidance, training and appropriate contextual information, helping ensure that existing principles are applied consistently. This strengthens confidence in qualitative judgement, reduces reliance on proxy indicators, and enables more informed and fair decisions.

3. A three-phase approach

- 3.1 Our reform will unfold through three connected phases (illustrated in **Figure 1**). This ensures that change is achievable and proportionate, that it is grounded in an accurate understanding of current practice, and that reforms build steadily as our evidence, experience and confidence grow. The approach aligns with institutional planning cycles, including the review of the University Strategy and the development of its successor. While Phase 1 has a particular emphasis on initial scoping and evidence-gathering, review and refinement will continue throughout Phases 2 and 3 as part of an iterative, learning-based approach to reform. Delivery of this reform programme will be supported by appropriate staff capacity, expertise and operational support.
- 3.2 Preparatory activity, including mobilisation, communications and initial planning, will take place from May–June 2026, with Phase 1 formally commencing in July 2026. Phase 2 will run from January 2028 to July 2030, followed by Phase 3 from August 2030 to July 2031.

Figure 1: Overview of three-phase approach

Phase 1: Understanding our practice and building foundations (scoping and design)

- 3.3 Phase 1 will focus on understanding how research is currently assessed across the University through a comprehensive audit of practices, criteria, indicators and decision-making processes, including mapping assessment practices across key institutional processes such as recruitment, promotion, REF and research planning. This will identify strengths, inconsistencies and risks, including any over-reliance on metrics or ranking proxies and any gaps in recognising outputs in diverse formats or languages. Alongside this evidence-gathering, we will make early, visible and low-risk improvements where issues are already clear. At the same time, we will put in place the core foundations for long-term reform by confirming governance arrangements, establishing key roles, articulating the University of Bristol's principles for responsible assessment, and building the communication and support structures needed for sustained change. Where issues are already well understood and improvements can be made safely and proportionately, we will implement early changes during Phase 1. This will allow the University to demonstrate tangible progress, build confidence and ensure that reform delivers meaningful benefits throughout the process.
- 3.4 This phase is intentionally designed as a scoping and co-design period. Using the SCOPE Framework, we will engage Schools, Faculties and staff across roles, disciplines and career stages to explore needs, test assumptions and identify priorities for reform. In parallel, we will draw on dialogue with selected external peers and strategic partners who are CoARA signatories, as well as relevant institutional initiatives such as the Perivoli Africa Research Centre, to ensure that perspectives from global and equitable research partnerships inform our approach. During this period, we will also consider what a light-touch but meaningful set of early indicators might look like, and how best to operationalise the separation between external reputation information and internal research assessment.
- 3.5 The outcome of Phase 1 will be an agreed, prioritised and resourced programme of reforms to be taken forward in Phase 2, rather than a pre-determined set of changes defined in advance. This will include defining what success looks like, how progress will be measured, and how benefits will be evaluated at appropriate stages.

Example 5: Supporting responsible institutional planning and target setting

Before responsible assessment

Institutional or faculty-level planning may rely heavily on simplified indicators such as citation metrics or grant income targets, which do not fully reflect research quality, disciplinary context or the full range of research contributions.

With responsible assessment

Planning and target setting are informed by a broader understanding of research quality, using appropriate indicators alongside qualitative judgement and contextual information. This supports more meaningful strategic planning, recognises diverse disciplinary strengths, and aligns planning processes with the University's academic values and long-term goals.

Phase 2: Embedding a holistic approach to research assessment

- 3.6 Phase 2 will focus on designing, piloting and embedding a more holistic and context-sensitive approach to research assessment across the University, informed by the findings and priorities identified in Phase 1 and by ongoing scoping, evaluation and engagement as reforms are developed and implemented. This may include revising guidance and criteria for recruitment,

promotion, REF preparation, internal evaluation and institutional planning processes to ensure alignment with responsible research assessment principles. We will continue to use the SCOPE Framework to guide implementation so that evaluation practice remains situated, co-designed and proportionate to purpose. This includes using evidence in ways that follow the principle of research being “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”, recognising both the value of openness and the importance of responsible data practice.

3.7 During this period, we will bring together the main strands of activity that shape how we understand, communicate and manage research quality, ensuring greater coherence between processes such as REF preparation, internal evaluation and planning cycles, alongside wider considerations such as disciplinary expectations, external positioning and financial sustainability. A coordinated Annual Research Quality Review will support Schools, Departments and other research units to reflect on their activity and achievements each year through multiple lenses, including qualitative judgement, REF criteria, disciplinary markers, responsible use of KPIs and, where relevant, contextualised reputation data. Through this consolidation and alignment, Phase 2 will deepen the use of qualitative judgement, reduce reliance on narrow indicators, and ensure that research assessment is coherent, transparent and supportive of the University’s wider goals.

Example 6: Recognising disciplinary diversity

Before responsible assessment

A researcher in a discipline with lower grant income potential feels disadvantaged in career progression due to income expectations that do not reflect disciplinary norms.

With responsible assessment

Assessment recognises disciplinary context and values diverse forms of excellence, supporting fairer and more appropriate evaluation.

3.8 We will also continue to share learning with the UK CoARA National Chapter and other networks, and will actively seek to exchange practice and, where appropriate, collaborate with partners in the GW4 Alliance and with the University of Bristol’s key strategic research partners in Europe and globally who are also signatories of CoARA. This will allow us to situate our own reforms in an international context, learn from comparable institutions, and contribute to the wider development of responsible research assessment practice.

Phase 3: Evaluating progress and planning the next cycle

3.9 Phase 3 will focus on understanding what has changed and what should come next. During this period, we will review institutional progress against all ten CoARA commitments and against the objectives set for the reforms implemented in Phase 2. We will evaluate the impact of the reforms on decision quality, research culture, equity and workload, and identify any areas that require further development or clarification. The Phase 3 evaluation will also reflect on how the SCOPE Framework has supported responsible practice and what has been learned about implementing change at scale.

3.10 Using what we learn, we will prepare the next five-year action plan, setting priorities, updating guidance and training, refining indicators for planning and assurance, and confirming the governance and support needed for the next cycle. The outcome will be a clear, evidence-informed roadmap that protects what is working, addresses remaining gaps, and positions the University of Bristol to lead responsibly in research assessment.

4. Action plan structure

- 4.1 The action plan is presented in two parts. [Appendix A](#) sets out the strategic framework for this five-year programme, showing at a high level the focus of each phase and how this contributes to delivery of the ten CoARA commitments. [Appendix B](#) sets out the process by which the University of Bristol will move from scoping and co-design to agreed, resourced and implemented reforms, including the approach to audit, consultation, prioritisation, decision-making and evaluation. This structure is intended to provide transparency and assurance about both the direction of travel and the machinery of delivery, while recognising that the specific content and sequencing of reforms will be determined through the Phase 1 process.
- 4.2 We will agree a light-touch and proportionate set of indicators during Phase 1, refine them as reforms are embedded in Phase 2, and use the resulting evidence to inform the Phase 3 evaluation and the development of the next action plan.

Example 7: Using rankings and reputation indicators appropriately

[Before responsible assessment](#)

Rankings and reputation indicators may be used in ways that are not clearly distinguished from academic quality assessment, or without sufficient contextual understanding. This can create uncertainty about how such indicators should inform decisions relating to recruitment, planning or research development.

[With responsible assessment](#)

Schools and Faculties are supported to develop clear and appropriate reputation strategies, recognising that rankings and reputation indicators can play an important role in areas such as international visibility and student recruitment. At the same time, internal assessment of research quality, recruitment and progression decisions are informed by a broader range of evidence, including qualitative judgement and disciplinary expertise. This ensures that reputation indicators are used appropriately and transparently, alongside other relevant considerations.

5. Document provenance, authorship and use of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI)

- 5.1 This action plan was authored by Helen Young, Director of Research Excellence, on behalf of the University of Bristol. It has been developed with input from members of the RRA WG, including (in alphabetical order by surname) Emily Bonnin, Suzy Cheeke, Miao He, Susan Jim, Caroline McKinnon, Celine Petitjean, Rachel Shimeld, Matthew Shute and Liam Taylor, and further refined through institutional review processes, with particular acknowledgement to Daniela Schmidt and Matthew Brown for their contributions to the final version. This action plan was recommended for approval by the Research Culture Committee and approved by the University Research Committee on 19 May 2026.
- 5.2 In preparing the initial drafts of this document, the author made limited and transparent use of AI tools, including Microsoft Copilot and ChatGPT, as drafting and editing aids. These tools were used to support tasks such as structuring text, refining language, testing clarity and coherence, and exploring alternative phrasings. As this work develops, consideration will be given to the appropriate use of AI and other digital tools to support aspects of implementation.
- 5.3 All substantive decisions about the content, structure, interpretation of the CoARA Agreement, and the commitments and approach set out in this action plan remain the responsibility of the University and its governance processes. The use of AI tools has not replaced expert judgement, institutional decision-making or collective deliberation, and no content has been included without human review, adaptation and approval.

Appendix A: Strategic framework for the CoARA action plan (2026–2031)

A1. Purpose

This Appendix sets out the strategic framework for the University of Bristol's five-year programme of reform to research assessment in line with the CoARA Agreement. It provides a high-level, phase-based view of the direction of travel, the main areas of focus in each phase, and how these contribute to delivery of the ten CoARA commitments. It does not pre-determine the specific content of individual reforms; these will be identified, prioritised and designed through the Phase 1 scoping and co-design process described in [Appendix B](#).

A2. Overview of the three phases

The University's reform programme is structured around three connected phases:

- **Phase 1 (2026–27):** Scoping, evidence-gathering and co-design
- **Phase 2 (2028–30):** Design, piloting and embedding of reforms
- **Phase 3 (2030–31):** Evaluation, consolidation and renewal

Together, these phases ensure that reform is evidence-led, participatory, proportionate and sustainable, and that it remains aligned with the CoARA principles and commitments. While each phase has a distinct primary focus, the work initiated in earlier phases will continue and evolve in later phases, so that reform is sustained and iterative rather than sequential and discontinuous.

A3. Strategic framework by phase

Phase 1: Understanding our practice and building foundations (July 2026 – December 2027)

Strategic focus:

- Build a robust institutional evidence base on how research is currently assessed.
- Identify strengths, gaps, risks and inconsistencies in current practices.
- Define and put in place the governance, principles, capability and support structures that are required for sustained reform.
- Use the SCOPE Framework to support structured, participatory scoping and option appraisal.
- Identify and prioritise the first wave of reforms to be taken forward in Phase 2.

Key strategic outcomes:

- A comprehensive map and audit of research assessment practices across the University.
- An agreed set of institutional principles for responsible research assessment.
- A prioritised, resourced and governance-approved reform roadmap for Phase 2.
- An agreed, light-touch and proportionate evaluation framework and initial indicators.

Primary CoARA commitments supported:

- C1 (Recognise diverse contributions and careers)
- C2 (Primacy of qualitative judgement)
- C3 (Abandon inappropriate use of metrics)
- C4 (Avoid inappropriate use of rankings)
- C5 (Commit resources)
- C6 (Review and develop criteria, tools and processes)

- C7 (Awareness, guidance and training)
- C8 (Exchange of practices)
- C10 (Evidence-informed evaluation)

Phase 2: Embedding a holistic approach to research assessment (January 2028 – July 2030)

Strategic focus:

- Design, pilot and embed a first wave of priority reforms identified in Phase 1.
- Align key institutional processes (e.g. REF preparation, internal evaluation, planning, promotion and review) within a coherent, holistic assessment framework.
- Strengthen the use of qualitative judgement and reduce reliance on narrow or proxy indicators.
- Build assessment capability through training, guidance and shared tools.
- Operationalise a clear separation between external reputation management and internal research assessment.
- Share learning nationally and internationally through CoARA and other networks.

Key strategic outcomes:

- New or revised assessment criteria, tools and processes embedded in priority areas.
- A coordinated Annual Research Quality Review operating across the institution.
- Updated policies and guidance reflecting CoARA-aligned practice.
- Increased consistency, transparency and contextualisation in assessment practice.
- Ongoing monitoring of impact on decision quality, culture, equity and workload.
- Increased awareness, understanding and consistent application of responsible research assessment principles across the research community.

Primary CoARA commitments supported:

C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6, C7, C8, C9 (Communicate progress), C10

Phase 3: Evaluating progress and planning the next cycle (August 2030 – July 2031)

Strategic focus:

- Evaluate the impact of reforms implemented during Phase 2.
- Review institutional progress against all ten CoARA commitments.
- Assess effects on decision quality, research culture, equity, workload and sustainability.
- Consolidate what is working and identify remaining gaps or risks.
- Prepare the next five-year action plan.

Key strategic outcomes:

- A formal, evidence-based evaluation of the University's CoARA implementation.
- An updated institutional self-assessment against the CoARA commitments.
- A refreshed and prioritised action plan for the next cycle.

Primary CoARA commitments supported:

- C9 (Communicate progress)
- C10 (Evidence-informed evaluation)
- Continued alignment with all other commitments.

Appendix B: Reform design and delivery approach

B1. Purpose

This Appendix sets out the process by which the University of Bristol will move from high-level commitment to specific, implemented reforms to research assessment. It explains how Phase 1 will operate as a structured scoping and co-design year, and how scoping, prioritisation, testing and refinement will continue iteratively through Phases 2 and 3 as reforms are developed, implemented and evaluated. This approach is intentionally designed to avoid pre-determining solutions and to ensure that reforms are context-sensitive, owned by the community, and sustainable.

B2. Principles underpinning the approach

The delivery of this action plan will be guided by the following principles:

- **Participation:** Those who are assessed, and those who assess, will be involved in shaping reforms.
- **Evidence-led:** Decisions will be grounded in audit, analysis and evaluation.
- **Context-sensitive:** Approaches will respect disciplinary, role-based and career-stage differences. They will also support equitable and inclusive research collaborations, including international partnerships, recognising contributions in ways that are consistent with principles such as those articulated in the [Africa Charter for Transformative Research Collaborations](#).
- **Proportionate:** Reforms will be targeted, prioritised and sequenced to avoid unnecessary burden or duplication.
- **Iterative:** Piloting, learning and refinement will be built in from the outset.
- **Transparent and fair:** Processes and criteria will be communicated clearly and supported by appropriate guidance and training, enabling those involved in research assessment and decision-making to apply responsible assessment principles consistently and confidently.

The SCOPE Framework will be used throughout to structure and support this work, and these principles will be operationalised through the phased programme of work set out below.

B3. Phase 1 activities: Scoping and co-design

During Phase 1, the University will:

1. Map the assessment landscape

- Identify all major research assessment touchpoints (e.g. recruitment, promotion, personal development review, internal funding, REF and strategic planning processes).

2. Audit current practice

- Review criteria, indicators, guidance, data sources and decision processes in use.
- Identify reliance on metrics, proxies or rankings, and areas of inconsistency or risk.

3. Analyse alignment with CoARA principles

- Conduct a gap and risk analysis against the CoARA commitments and institutional principles.

4. Engage the community using the SCOPE Framework

- Run structured workshops and consultations across roles, disciplines and career stages.
- Test assumptions, surface priorities, and explore reform options and risks.

5. Engage external peers and strategic partners

- Identify key external peers and strategic partners, including comparator institutions who are CoARA signatories.
- Establish contact points and mechanisms for sharing practice and learning about research assessment reform.
- Draw on perspectives from global and equitable research partnerships, including relevant institutional initiatives such as the Perivoli Africa Research Centre, to inform our approach.
- Use insights from these external peers and strategic partners to inform option appraisal, prioritisation and risk assessment.

6. Develop options and priorities

- Identify potential areas for reform.
- Assess them against agreed criteria (e.g. impact, feasibility, risk, readiness, dependencies).

7. Agree success criteria and evaluation approach

- Define what success looks like and how it will be measured, supporting continuous learning and refinement throughout implementation.

8. Confirm resourcing and delivery model

- Identify required capacity, capability and budget.
- Agree governance and programme management arrangements.

9. Secure institutional decisions

- Present a prioritised, resourced Phase 2 reform programme for approval through the agreed governance route.

B4. Prioritisation framework

Potential reforms will be prioritised using criteria such as:

- Contribution to CoARA commitments and institutional strategy.
- Expected impact on decision quality, culture and fairness.
- Feasibility and resource requirements.
- Risk and potential unintended consequences.
- Readiness of the organisation and dependencies on other changes.

This will enable an initial set of reforms for Phase 2 to be identified, with others sequenced for later phases.

B5. Governance and decision-making

Delivery of the action plan will be overseen by the Responsible Research Assessment Working Group (RRA WG). Strategic oversight and formal approvals will be provided through the Research Culture Committee (RCC) and the University Research Committee (URC), with escalation to the Academic Leadership Board (ALB) and/or the University Executive Board (UEB) as appropriate. Where specific reforms relate to processes or frameworks owned by other governance bodies (for example, promotion and progression, REF governance, equality and inclusion, or digital and data governance), proposals will also be taken through the relevant committees and decision-making routes in line with established University governance.

Key decision points will include:

- Approval of Phase 2 reform priorities and resourcing at the end of Phase 1.
- Approval of major policy or framework changes during Phase 2, through the appropriate governance routes.
- Approval of the Phase 3 evaluation and the next action plan.

B6. From Phase 1 to Phase 2: Turning priorities into programmes

For each approved Phase 2 reform area:

- A clear scope, objectives, timeline and ownership will be defined.
- Co-design groups will be established where appropriate.
- Pilots will be used to test approaches before full roll-out.
- Legacy criteria and processes will be formally withdrawn or revised to avoid dual systems.

B7. Evaluation and learning

Evaluation will operate at three levels:

- Ongoing monitoring (during Phase 2): workload, consistency, uptake, and immediate effects.
- Impact evaluation (during Phase 3): effects on decision quality, research culture, equity and sustainability.
- Strategic review: alignment with CoARA commitments and institutional goals.

Findings will be published internally and shared, where appropriate, through CoARA and other sector networks. They will also be used to inform ongoing scoping, reprioritisation and adjustment of reform activities during Phase 2, as well as the design of the subsequent CoARA action plan.

B8. International collaboration and peer learning

In addition to engagement through the UK CoARA National Chapter and other sector networks, the University of Bristol will actively seek to build and sustain links with its key strategic research partners in Europe and globally who are also signatories of CoARA. Where helpful, this may include establishing a light-touch virtual network or forum for sharing practice, discussing challenges, and exploring opportunities for alignment or collaboration in specific areas of reform. We will also explore opportunities for regional peer learning and collaborative leadership through established strategic partnerships, including the GW4 Alliance.

This international peer engagement will inform both the initial scoping and prioritisation of reforms and the ongoing refinement of approaches during Phase 2, helping to ensure that the University's work is informed by, and contributes to, the wider international reform landscape.

B9. Relationship to future cycles

This process is designed to be repeatable. Phase 3 evaluation and learning will feed directly into the design of the next five-year CoARA action plan, ensuring continuous improvement rather than one-off reform.